

TECHNOLOGIES USED INFORMATION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMBAT AND IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Annotation: The article reveals the concept of information-psychological impact, threats to national security in the information sphere are disclosed, the term "psychological operations" is considered in detail, technologies of information-psychological impact are formulated.

Key words: psychological operations, national security, technology, threats, information and psychological impact, terrorist organizations.

Today, we are witnessing the processes of transformation of both the world community and the social structure and way of life within our state with the active use of communications of various kinds. We really feel the persistent information and psychological impact on our consciousness through the media (television, radio, press, social networks, etc.), thus choosing a clear and stable position of our independent state, in the minds of every citizen, is a priority. In the process of globalization, our society cannot remain indifferent to the processes taking place in the world, since it is communications that are the condition for the progress of Uzbekistan and its integration into the world order as a whole.

On January 13, 2022, an expanded meeting of the Security Council was held at the National Defense Control Center chaired by the Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, during the meeting, members of the Security Council, the command staff of the Armed Forces and the heads of the military administrative sectors, as one of the priority tasks was determined: "In the current situation of increasing threats in the global information space, the urgency of ensuring information security, protecting young people from alien ideas, psychological training of military personnel and strengthening morale is growing, it was emphasized at the meeting" [1].

The basis of the defense doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the monitoring of threats and dangers throughout the territory of Uzbekistan, directly or indirectly related to the interests of the economy, politics and integrity of the

country. One of the main threats to national security in the military sphere is: Ideological and psychological actions in the information and communication space, directed against the sovereignty, independence, territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and posing a threat to the peaceful life of citizens [2].

The global processes of information globalization dictate not only the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the economy and spheres of life of the country, but also the conditions for ensuring the security of information systems. Uzbekistan was one of the first in Central Asia to join the international security system in the field of information and communication technologies. The Center for Information Security under the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been established in the state and is effectively carrying out its activities in the field of information security.

The general phrase that civilizations are created by communications, and globalization, this is the process of their development, should be "decomposed" into types of specific tools that allow you to do this: formatting and shaping certain characteristics of civilization with the help of communication mechanisms. This is not only an intense impact on sociosystems in the form of, for example, color and velvet revolutions, but also an evolutionary development, when the consequences of communicative innovations can begin to be felt centuries later. And evolutionary and revolutionary communicative actions transform sociosystems, only at different speeds.

Below we will consider two types of transitions. On the one hand, these are examples of transitions, when the transformation of communication brings as a consequence the transformation of civilization. On the other hand, those types of scientific directions that explore the processes of these transformations from different positions.

The famous scientist G. Innis wrote a lot about the influence of information carriers (papyrus, parchment, paper as an example) on the formation and functioning of civilizations. It was he who formed the principle according to which the state seeks to create a connection in space, and religion - in time, and the Roman Empire was saved when it switched to cheaper papyrus, which helped its expansion [5].

There are, however, questions about religion's exclusive focus on temporal connection. After all, religion in the form of missionary work is just as active in building up ties in space. Rather, we can say that religion, like culture, works with other types of texts that do not "burn out" as quickly as the texts of the

state. They remain the same for many generations. But they are hostile to the entry of other such long-term texts.

The state sees danger in information wars coming from outside, religion sees danger in semantic ones. And if in Muslim countries there is still a large link between the state and religion, then there the state will be sensitive to semantic interventions as well. For this reason, for example, the Barbie doll becomes impossible for Iran, because it is an alien long-term product, along with which comes an alien model of the world.

Communication-civilization tools are such changes in communications (evolutionary or revolutionary) that lead to cardinal transformations of sociosystems. In some cases, communication can act as a Bradbury butterfly, when a small action leads to significant consequences.

One of the main influences in the communicative-civilizational toolkit is the information-psychological influence. Information and psychological impact is a purposeful production and dissemination of special information that has a direct impact (positive or negative) on the functioning and development of the information and psychological environment of society, the psyche and behavior of the political elite and the population of the state [3].

In NATO countries, the whole range of measures of information and psychological impact on the troops and population of the enemy is denoted by the term "psychological operations". In 2010, the US leadership announced a transition in the field of information and psychological confrontation to the concept of "strategic communications". According to his plan, strategic communications are a purposeful activity of all US government structures aimed at creating, improving and maintaining conditions favorable for achieving national interests through the implementation of plans, the development of the main directions of the content of foreign policy propaganda, the preparation and dissemination of information and propaganda materials agreed with the actions of all branches of government.

In August 2011, MISO Command (Fort Bragg, North Carolina) was activated. MISOs are at the core of strategic communications. According to American experts, such operations are a vital part of a wide range of political, military, economic and ideological actions used by the American leadership to achieve national goals. The purpose of MISO is to disseminate information to foreign audiences in support of US policy and national goals.

It is possible to single out a number of theoretical provisions used by specialists when using the technology of information and psychological impact in a number of modern armed conflicts.

The Simulacrum technology (simulacrum is an image without an original, a representation of what does not really exist) consists in the fact that with the help of the media a virtual image of an event (fact, object, process) is created that did not exist and does not exist in real life. In essence, the “media is the reality” of an event that has nothing to do with real life is being created. This is not just a distortion of an event, but such a transformation of it, when it becomes different in meaning, occurs at a different time, with different consequences. Once born, the simulacrum can lead a rich social life.

The simulacrum can function using the Carousel technology.

The «Carousel» technology consists in the sequential promotion of fabricated information (simulacrum) through the stages of «assumption - citation - approval - replication». The practical use of this technology can be clearly seen in the information and psychological actions used by Ukraine. Thus, the Minister of Defense of Ukraine suggests that Russian combat units have concentrated on the border to invade Ukraine (“assumption”). The US State Department claims that “according to” the Ukrainian Defense Ministry, Russian troops have prepared for the invasion (“citation”). Then representatives of the political leadership of Ukraine claim that, according to the American intelligence services, an invasion of Russian troops into Ukraine is being prepared (“approval”). Finally, the media picks up on this canard and retells it in the most incredible contexts, subsequently referring to each other (“replication”).

The «Gadget» technology consists in the fact that information is transmitted using modern communication technologies available to communication devices that are widely introduced into everyday life of citizens: via social networks and to personal email addresses via computers, i-Pad tablets, mini i-Pad, smartphones; via SMS and MMS messages via cell phones, smartphones; through television channels through television networks; through video and audio recordings using video and audio players.

With the help of gadget technologies, many processes were controlled during the «March of Millions» demonstration on Bolotnaya Square in Moscow, Russian Federation (May 6, 2012), the coup d'état in Ukraine and the events on Independence Square (2013-2014).

Within the framework of the technology under consideration, the «YouTube» (“Idol Creation Technology”) technology can be used, which consists in the fact

that the YouTube Internet service popular with users is assigned the status of an objective and authoritative source of information and specific video information from it is recognized as trustworthy information.

The effectiveness of this technology lies in the fact that behind this Internet service there is a huge number of participants and fans, many of whom start their every day by browsing this portal.

The Blogger technology is based on the communicative properties of an opinion leader. Its essence lies in the fact that at the first stage an attractive image of a number of Internet blogs and bloggers is formed, their social status in various online audiences is increased in every possible way. At the second stage, bloggers begin to disseminate certain information, form the position of their audience, and in the event of a crisis, they give clear instructions on how to proceed.

«Psacing» technology (Jen Psaki technology) is based on the specifics of people's perception of information associated with the readiness of most people to quickly perceive simplified information about current events than complex, intellectually rich messages. The choice for the role of the official representative of the US State Department of the rustic and narrow-minded (but quite possibly playing such a role) Jennifer Psaki is not accidental. It provides several informational effects:

practically removes responsibility from the official source of information (the State Department) and shifts it to a charming simpleton who does not know elementary geography, history and political science;

inaccuracies, stupidities expressed by such a source, outside the context of their subsequent exposure, are easily perceived by a mass audience;

part of the audience, close to Psaki in terms of intellectual development, it seems that corrosive correspondents are biased towards her. This gives rise to a feeling of pity, contributes to the approval of her position, makes her an opinion leader.

Ebola technology (hemorrhagic fever) is based on the mechanism of reflex fixation of stimuli coinciding in time and the laws of association building.

USA President Barack Obama, who has been distinguished by a very unfriendly policy towards the Russian Federation, speaking at various forums, names Ebola, terrorism and Russia among the most dangerous threats to humanity. According to the law of associations, a part of the audience forms the image of Russia as an extreme and deadly threat, which must be fought with all available means.

The technology of «Black water» consists in the fact that non-state paramilitary groups (private - military companies) are sent into the camp of the enemy, the main goal of which is to play off the civilian population with law enforcement agencies and power, to generate conflict, confrontation, war, revolution. Snipers from such groups can simultaneously hit both military personnel and civilians, giving rise to mutual aggression and hatred in them. A striking example is the actions of groups of snipers during the coup d'état in Ukraine and the events on the Maidan (2013-2014) [4].

New trends in the field of information-psychological confrontation and the technologies discussed above, of course, require study and comprehensive understanding. However, already today we must determine the main ways to protect servicemen from enemy psychological operations.

Forecasting topics, channels and methods of impact can be carried out with the help of constant monitoring of risks and threats to the security of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the political, economic and military spheres with careful analytical work aimed at studying possible options for their development, real opportunities for their localization and elimination.

Prevention of psychological operations involves the implementation of a set of measures aimed at reducing the susceptibility and commitment of servicemen to the information and psychological impact of the enemy.

Disruption of information-psychological actions of the enemy involves the rapid identification of the means of information influence of the enemy, their immediate suppression and destruction.

Elimination of the consequences of negative information and psychological impact on servicemen includes: regular monitoring of the psychological state of each serviceman and unit as a whole in the course of performing a combat mission; systematic analysis and evaluation of the results of the effectiveness of the enemy's psychological impact; identifying the most vulnerable military personnel and providing them with practical assistance, if necessary, conducting psycho-rehabilitation with military personnel; restoration of organization and combat capability of the unit; the application of measures of appropriate influence to the guilty, alarmists, traitors, deserters; determination of a set of measures to optimize the entire countermeasure system.

Since the work defined above in each special unit should be carried out by a specialist psychologist, it is proposed, based on the experience of the special unit "snow leopard" of the People's Armed Militia of the People's Republic of China, to determine in each unit a part of freelance psychologists from among the most

trained military personnel under the sergeant's contract. These psychologists-instructors should practically participate in the performance of the combat mission of their unit in a regular position (for example, a shooter, a sapper specialist, etc.) for their intended purpose and directly conduct complex psychological work at the site of the task during preparation, during and after completion accomplishment of the combat mission.

It is advisable to train these certified psychologists-instructors under the guidance of full-time psychologists of the units, followed by the preparation of analytical reports on the level of psychological readiness of each serviceman, each unit and the unit as a whole, at psychological support courses for special forces units created at the training centers of law enforcement agencies, followed by regular the frequency of advanced training of these servicemen under the guidance of specialists in the field of military psychology.

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